

Ammonia volatilization losses from flooded rice soils

K. L. Sahrawat, postdoctoral research fellow, Soil Chemistry Department, International Rice Research Institute

Ammonium (NH_4^+) may be lost by volatilization from surface-applied fertilizers, from ammonium-forming fertilizers such as urea, and through diffusion from the soil to the surface. Some recent reports suggest that the losses could be as high as 50%. The loss has been attributed largely to the increased pH of the surface water caused by CO_2 , depletion due to photosynthesis by aquatic organisms, mainly algae.

The loss of NH_4^+ through volatilization from four soils of varying pH was assessed by the open- and closed-bottle technique. Nitrogen was broadcast at 100 kg N/ha as ammonium sulfate at 2 weeks after transplanting. The pH of the flood water

1. Influence of soil properties on cumulative loss of N as NH_3 gas. IRRI.

of those soils was monitored during 15 days of study.

The total nitrogen loss through ammonia volatilization during the first 15 days was highest in alkalinized Maahas clay and lowest in Luisiana clay (Fig.1).

Figure 2 shows a striking relationship

2. pH of the flood water of four tropical soils after application of ammonium sulfate. IRRI.

between changes in pH and ammonia losses through volatilization. In alkali soil, the pH of the flood water ranged from 9 to 9.9 during the 15 days; in other soils it was lower. In Luisiana clay, where pH was lowest, ammonia volatilization losses were also lowest.

Environment and its influence

Mechanism of the effect of gibberellin on rice

F. Aleshin, doctor of biological science and professor; N. Aleshin; E. Avakyan, candidate of biological science; and T. Satalkina, candidate of agricultural science, Laboratory of Physiology of Rice, Department of Plant Physiology and Biochemistry, Kuban Agricultural Institute, Kalinina 13, Krasnodar 350044 USSR

Treating rice with gibberellins causes the stems to elongate and become more slender, and thus to lodge. The silica of the cell walls of the treated plants was found to be similar to that of untreated plants. In treated plants, tillering was depressed, branching increased, the incidence of sterile panicles was marked, and yield was reduced.

Application of gibberellic acid (GA) to rice plants decreased the riboflavin and endogenous thiamine contents of the leaf and increased the level of leaf thiamine and thiamine diphosphoric acid

coccarboxylase. GA inhibited flavin oxidase markedly, causing indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) to accumulate. The RNA:DNA ratio in the growth apex of GA-treated rice increased. Although the total protein content of the rice plants remained constant, the amount of the electrophoretically mobile fraction of acid albumins declined. The total content of free amino acids decreased, but the levels of the different amino acids varied. The content of free proline decreased markedly and the histone content increased; the flow of the messenger system from the nuclei into the cytoplasm was shortened. GA probably affected the messenger system.

In summary, the mechanism of the effect of GA may be described as: GA decreases the content of the flower-initiating regulator (proline); promotes the accumulation of the repressor-blocking group of genes for reproduction (histone); and promotes IAA accumulation.

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